

The first record of *Austrodomus gamsberg* (Araneae: Prodidomidae) from South Africa

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INTRODUCTION

The Prodidomidae is a small spider family, with only 196 species in 24 genera globally (World Spider Catalog, 2025). The family is particularly rich in South Africa, with six genera and 29 species having been recorded thus far (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). The Afrotropical fauna of the subfamily Prodidominae (excluding *Theuma* Simon, 1893 and *Prodidomus* Hentz, 1847) was revised by Rodrigues & Rheims (2020), with five genera revised and three new genera described. As part of that study, two South African species of *Austrodomus* Lawrence, 1947 were redescribed, *A. scaber* (Purcell, 1904) and *A. zuluensis* Lawrence, 1947, and *A. gamsberg* Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020 was described from Namibia.

In March 2023, the University of the Free State held their annual field excursion at the Witsand Nature Reserve in the Northern Cape for the first time. This sampling effort greatly improved knowledge of arachnid biodiversity in the 2822 degree-square grid, which was one of the historically undersampled parts of the country (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Van der Mescht *et al.*, 2024). Among the many species recorded from the reserve for the first time was a single male specimen of *A. gamsberg*, representing the first record of the species from South Africa. Here we present images of the specimen, which was also successfully sequenced for the DNA barcoding gene (cytochrome oxidase subunit I, COI). This sequence is available on the SPIZA project on the Barcode of Life Data System (BOLD, www.boldsystems.org).

Austrodomus gamsberg Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020

Figures 1–3

General habitus of male as in Fig. 1; small spider, 2.32 mm in total length, with bright yellow carapace and legs; abdomen creamy-yellow dorsally and ventrally. Palp as in Figs 2 and 3; ventral RTA blunt and subrectangular in lateral view, dorsal RTA short and broad, with blunt, ventrally directed tip; embolus almost transverse, with median swelling on outer surface.

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Witsand Nature Reserve, Viewing Point, -28.5831, 22.4832, 1225 m a.s.l., 24.III.2023, leg. C. Haddad & R. Booyesen (under rocks, rocky hillside), 1m (NMBA 18624).

DNA Barcode: SPIZA1481-23.

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FIGURES 1–3. *Austrodomus gamsberg*, male. 1. Dorsal habitus; 2. Palp, ventral view; 3. Palp, retrolateral view.

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